

TRADE POLICIES AND AGRICULTURAL OUTPUT IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This paper focuses on trade policy and agricultural output in Nigeria. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design. Data analysed cover the period 1990-2021, and were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin and World Development Indicators (WDI). Ordinary Least Square (OLS) Estimation Technique was adopted and the results indicated a positive and significant relationship between exchange rate and agriculture output; a negative and significant relationship between trade openness and agriculture output; and a negative and significant relationship between tariff and agriculture output. It was concluded that trade policy has a significant relationship with agriculture output. In view of this, the paper recommended the adoption of a managed-float exchange rate regime to accommodate the peculiarities of agriculture sector. To increase the output of the sector and by extension, export proceeds from agriculture, it is recommended that security, high cost of funds, and adequate provision for processing of farm output should form the lynchpin of government policy in the agricultural sector; this should include concession for agricultural farm inputs

Introduction

Trade policies are essentially government policies that impact exports and imports of goods and services. They define the extent and pattern of a country's trade with the rest of the world. The effectiveness of trade policies can be measured by the extent of growth and development that they have engendered in the economy, especially in the agricultural sector (Ogunjinmi & Oduyoye-Ejumedina, 2021). Trade and trade policy reforms are part of a set of economic instruments and institutional arrangements that facilitate transactions in a predictable, consistent, and sustainable manner to achieve better allocation of resources.

After independence, Nigeria adopted different policy measures to enhance production and productivity in the real sector of the economy, with a view to promoting its trade relations. Some of these policies were directed at the development of the domestic economy through either the promotion of exports or the restriction of imports as a means to greater resource employment, productivity, and output diversification.

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Some of the trade policies adopted included Import Substitution Industrialization (ISI), Export Promotion (EP), and the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) (Effiom and Ebi, 2021).

Import Substitution Industrialization was more restrictive and pursued the objective of scaling down Nigeria's import volume while encouraging the local production of goods with large import elasticity. On the other hand, the export promotion policy advocated for the production of goods for export and greater trade liberalisation for enhanced competitiveness of local products. Consequently, the Structural Adjustment Programme had deeper effects on all sectors of the economy. At the national level, SAP altered the pattern and trend of production and consumption while imposing an import ban on certain basic commodities. Despite these policies, the performance of key sectors of the country's economy, including the agricultural sector, did not show marked improvement.

Apart from these earlier policies, the government implemented several initiatives and programmes to enhance agricultural sector productivity. These included the Agriculture Promotion Policy (APP), Nigeria-Africa Trade and Investment Promotion Programme, Presidential Economic Diversification Initiative, Economic and Export Promotion Incentives and the Zero Reject Initiative; Reducing Emission from Deforestation and Forest Degradation (REDD+), Nigeria Erosion and Watershed Management Project (NEWMAP), Action Against Desertification (AAD) Programme, among others. These efforts were aimed at improving agricultural productivity to ensure a sufficient supply of food to meet domestic demands as well as export. Besides, they were aimed at reversing forest loss and degradation, promotion of sustainable management of natural resources, rehabilitation of degraded lands, and reducing erosion and climate vulnerability.

Despite these efforts, Nigeria's agricultural sector is faced with many challenges that impact its productivity. These challenges include poor land tenure systems, low levels of irrigation farming, climate change, and land degradation. Others are low technology, high production costs, poor distribution of inputs, limited financing, high post-harvest losses, and poor access to markets. These challenges have stifled agricultural productivity, thereby affecting the sector's contribution to the country's GDP as well as increased food imports due to population rise hence declining levels of food sufficiency. For instance, between 2016 and 2019, Nigeria's cumulative agricultural imports stood at N3.35 trillion, four times higher than the agricultural exports of N803 billion within the same period.

Information in recent times has shown that a decrease in Nigerian agricultural exports is a result of price instability on the international market (Osabohien, Obiekwe,

Urhie, & Sabuohien 2018; Osabohien *et al.* 2019). Compared to manufactured products imported from advanced countries, agricultural products are less competitive, resulting in trade deficits. Nigeria has 70.8 million hectares of agricultural land area with maize, cassava, guinea corn, yam beans, millet, and rice being the major crops. Nigeria's rice production rose from 3.7 million metric tonnes in 2017 to 4.0 million metric tonnes in 2018. Despite this, only 57 percent of the 6.7 million metric tonnes of rice consumed in Nigeria annually is locally produced, leading to a deficit of about 3 million metric tonnes, which is either imported or smuggled into the country illegally. Agriculture has the distinguished feature of low prices, resulting in unfavourable terms of trade. The low earnings from the export of agricultural commodities are due to a decrease in production of agricultural commodities that made emerging economies rely on the importation of food (Osabohien & Osuagwu, 2017).

Trade policy reforms were intended to encourage the non-oil industry, particularly the rural agricultural sector, with the hope of alleviating pastoral poverty and disparity (Udoh and Adelaja, 2021). Similarly, various agricultural programmes and strategies in the country have been seen to coexist with food crop output and price volatility. The drive towards export promotion will boost an emerging nation's economic growth through the multiplier effects of exports on the income level of the country; this is because income earned through exports helps to enhance the aggregate demand in the country. The information on the sensitivity of export supply to price changes and non-price variables had been critical in the development of a comprehensive, broad export policy package.

The agricultural sector has experienced low production output due to self-inflicted factor of massive importation of food items to feed the teeming population. The nation also lags behind in the supply of food production for her citizens (Nwanji, Lawal, Asamu, & Inegbedion, 2019). It therefore results in a great deal of issues with respect to the country's agricultural advancement. The agricultural inefficiency hinders the essential opportunities for climate change mitigation and affects the sector's productivity regarding food security, unemployment, and poverty. To ensure productivity in the agricultural sector, the different trade policies (relating to the exchange of goods and services in the international market) adopted by the Nigerian government have not recorded much success. Meanwhile, improving the agricultural sector is a necessary condition for food security, tackling the risks associated with agrarian intensification, especially for climate-smart agricultural practices.

Prior to and shortly after independence, the government was a major player in the rural agricultural sector, both as a producer and facilitator. Before the commencement of the SAP (Structural Adjustment Programme) in June 1986, rural

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poverty and income distribution activities were largely related to agricultural development since the majority of the rural labour force was engaged by this sector. Thus, agricultural development and rural development were seen to be synonymous. A major framework for implementing agriculture-related trade policies included a Marketing Board Policy, through which all exportable agricultural products were purchased by the boards on behalf of the government at prices far lower than world prices, thus regulating the reward to rural labour.

In order to boost production and diversify the export base, the government embarked on an economic reform package as a channel to increase incentives for the agricultural sector. This was hatched with the intention of increasing rural income by attracting resources to the rural economy. Unquestionably, the exchange rate reform measure was the most profound trade policy reform measure introduced since 1986 in terms of getting prices right and boosting rural income and agricultural productivity. At the commencement of the reform measures, it was argued that the domestic currency, which was administratively fixed by the relevant monetary authority, was highly overvalued.

Major exchange rate re-alignments were needed if the goal of stimulating agricultural production and exports were to be achieved. It should be noted that exchange rate reforms were aimed not only at the agricultural sector but also at addressing external sector imbalances and improving competitiveness. Hence, it was expected that the prices of agricultural exports would rise in terms of domestic currency value if major reform measures (in the form of a series of devaluations) were carried out. In this arrangement, the rate at which the domestic currency was exchanged for a unit of major international currencies was determined by market forces with minimal intervention by the government.

A prominent exchange rate policy measure in the 1980s and 1990s was the setting up of a second-tier foreign exchange market (SFEM) as a mechanism for securing a more market-friendly rate for the naira and aligning relative prices so as to enhance efficiency in resource allocation and promote domestic-based production and non-oil exports. As a policy objective, the liberalisation and deregulation of the exchange control regime were designed to facilitate and enhance trading activities. Items on the import prohibition list have over time been drastically reduced, with the government opting to utilise tariff structures to protect end-user product pricing of local industries and discourage frivolous imports.

Aside from the radical exchange rate reform measures embarked on since 1986, numerous tariff and non-tariff measures were also implemented with the aim of stimulating production and exports of non-oil goods, particularly agricultural

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commodities. In general, trade policy reforms were largely designed to provide incentives for the non-oil sector, particularly the rural agricultural sector, with the hope that rural poverty and inequality would be reduced.

Some specific trade liberalisation measures undertaken under the SAP included the removal of bureaucratic controls on trade. The import licencing regime, together with exchange control on all current account transactions, was abolished as soon as exchange liberalisation began in September 1986. The abolition of commodity marketing boards was also followed by the abolition of the export prohibition for most items and a reduction in the number of prohibited imported items. The early years of the reform saw the introduction of a new export finance facility, and a financing and rediscount facility was put in place to assist private exporters by providing refinancing for the export of both agricultural and non-agricultural products. These measures were supported by the introduction of a duty drawback/suspension scheme, which was aimed at enabling exporters to import raw materials and intermediate products for use in the manufacturing of export products. It could be observed that trade policy measures were not only aimed at diversifying the export base of the country but also to add value to the export of agricultural produce.

By 1995, more emphasis was placed on a market-oriented exchange rate system to enhance export competitiveness. A new seven-year tariff reform programme was also introduced, with frequent adjustments and changes to the tariff structure. As at 2004, the applied tariff rate averaged about 25 percent, with some exceeding 100 percent. Currently, Nigeria maintains a 150 percent ceiling rate on all agricultural goods. In general, recourse to quantitative restrictions on imports is on the decline; Nigeria still bans imports of such products as maize, sorghum, millet, wheat flour, vegetables, and plastic articles. Nigeria also enforces a ban for health reasons on all types of meat.

From the foregoing, it can be deduced that trade policy in Nigeria has focused both on relative price incentives (in terms of exchange rate and tariff adjustments) and quantitative restrictions in terms of quota and outright ban. Furthermore, trade policy practices in Nigeria aim to minimise external imbalances. In other words, it is aimed at curtailing the incessant importation of consumer goods and protecting domestic production.

Primarily, agriculture has been the dominant sector of the Nigerian external sector. Despite these numerous policies, as adumbrated above, cursory perusal of the performance of the sector relative to the plethora of policy reforms, including exchange rate liberalisation, trade liberalisation, and a regulated tariff regime, has not impacted significantly on the export of agricultural output. For instance, between 2016 and 2019, Nigeria's cumulative agricultural imports stood at N3.35 trillion, four times higher than

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the agricultural exports of N803 billion within the same period. Given the level of Nigerian agricultural imports relative to her exports, it is imperative to examine the extent to which Nigerian trade policy contributes to these two phenomena.

The objectives of this paper are to examine the relationship between foreign exchange liberalisation and agriculture sector performance in Nigeria, the relationship between trade openness and agriculture output in Nigeria, and the relationship between tariff liberalisation and agriculture output in Nigeria.

Literature review

Conceptual Framework

Agriculture is crucial to the economy, and farming provides a livelihood to over 60% of the Nigerian population, although only 40% of the arable land is cultivated. Nigeria's agricultural sector has been in decline over the past four decades. Between 1970 and 1985, Nigeria's trade policy with reference to agriculture took the form of foreign exchange control, quantitative restrictions, and tariffs (Manyong et al., 2005). Two critical instruments defined Nigeria's trade policy, namely, the encouragement of exports of agricultural products via the eradication of export duties on export crops and the eradication or reduction in duties charged on agricultural imports: food, inputs, raw materials, agricultural equipment, and machinery (Effiom and Ebi, 2021). In 2011, the government embarked on two new policies—the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA) and the Agricultural Promotion Policy (2016–2020)—to transform agriculture from a development-oriented to an agribusiness-focused industry based on integrated value chains. To this end, several programmes are in place; incentives are available to farmers to increase domestic production of certain commodities (such as cassava, rice, and wheat); and several import prohibitions and restrictions are imposed on agricultural products. Nonetheless, the sector still faces various challenges, including shortages of feedstock as inputs, poorly maintained drainage systems, and poor transport networks that prevent the timely transfer of agricultural goods to markets.

Empirically, studies have argued that the transformation from agriculture to industry is a movement from traditional to modern (Ikenwa., Sulaimon, & Kuje, 2017; Sertoglu, Ugural, & Bekun, 2017; Ogunjinmi and Oduyoye-Ejumedina, 2021). Furthermore, it can be affirmed that trade has an influence on agricultural performance in Nigeria because there is hardly any development plan or structural reform in Nigeria that undermines the agricultural sector. However, the problem has always been the lack of implementation of government trade policies in this direction.

Udoh and Adelaja (2021) observe that agricultural trade policies are generally among the subtlest in any international trade discussion. This assertion is predicated on

the fact that, in Nigeria, agricultural policies have faced four main phases from 1960 to 1969, followed by 1970 to 1979 during the period of the oil boom, also from 1980 to the late 1990s during the structural adjustment programme (SAP), and lastly during the implementation of the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS) agenda. During the era of the SAP agenda in Nigeria, the emphasis was mainly on the dispersal of the export base away from the oil sector and emerging non-oil earnings from foreign exchange. In order to realise this, lots of policy reformation and incentives were created to stimulate the trade of non-oil tradable imports and, likewise, expand the Nigerian export market.

The government employed a financial reform package as a network to increase the inducement to the agricultural sector in order to raise productivity and grow the export base. Trade policy reforms were intended in order to encourage the non-oil industry, particularly the rural agricultural sector, with the hope of alleviating pastoral poverty and disparity (Udoh & Adelaja, 2021). Similarly, various agricultural programmes and strategies in the country have been seen to coexist with food crop output and price volatility. The information on the sensitivity of export supply to price changes and non-price variables was critical in the development of a comprehensive, broad export policy package. In any scenario, if export supply reacts unfavourably to price changes, price changes cannot result in an increase in export volume. As a result, government rules and regulations in the agriculture sector are essential. Agriculture production and export earnings, on the other hand, will rise due to favourable policies.

Furthermore, the Agricultural Transformation Agenda draft document (2011) remarked that instruments of trade policy such as import tariffs, export duties, and quantitative limitations on imports and exports in Nigeria impacted input and output prices of agricultural commodities. Theoretically, agricultural policies are supposed to affect various phases of agriculture. Implementation of agricultural policies is intended to accomplish detailed goals like an increase in level of production, availability of farm inputs, an upsurge in value addition, and a decrease in food prices, among others (Ayinde., Ilori, Babatunde, & Ayinde, 2015).

Verter and Bečvařova (2016), in a study, revealed that a vibration to agricultural exports can lead to variation in the long run, to the alteration of economic growth. However, Emerole and Edeoga (2013) note that the export of non-oil agriculture has the potential of contributing to the country's economic growth. Yet, the nature of foreign exchange management constitutes the foremost challenge. Moreover, Ekiran., Awe, and Ogunjobi (2014) are of the opinion that an appropriate policy combination needs to be put in place by the government in order to network the influx of capital towards the expansion of agricultural productivity in the process of upsurge of agricultural exports to achieve economic development in Nigeria.

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Orji et al. (2019) observe that, prior to the oil boom of the 1970's, Nigeria operated a fixed exchange rate system. This system helped to maintain a stable exchange rate and also helped the country to preserve the value of her external reserves. During this period, the agriculture sector was a major contributor to Nigeria's total GDP. Agriculture was the mainstay of the economy, and it provided food and employment for the populace as well as raw materials for the nascent industrial sector. The sector was also responsible for generating the bulk of government revenue and foreign exchange earnings, and its average share of GDP was about 55.8%.

According to NEEDS (2004), Nigeria's agricultural policy aims to ensure food security, promote domestic trade, enhance foreign exchange earnings, promote export diversification, enhance access to agricultural raw materials, encourage participation in preferential trade arrangements, and promote the use of modern technology and the quality of agricultural exports. During the period of NEEDS, the Federal Government provided support for: research activities and farmers for the development of high-yielding, disease resistant and heat-tolerant seed varieties; the stabilisation of market prices for fertilisers; the improvement of extension services; and the development of new fertilizers. Support for research activities is said to have been fruitful. The National Seed Service (NSS) continues to, inter alia, produce and distribute seeds, upgrade seed processing plants, produce seed certification tags, and engage in seed testing and seed crop inspection.

Agriculture facilitates development in an economy not only through its contribution of raw materials and inputs for manufacturing but also through the use of agricultural products as exports for enhanced foreign exchange earnings and revenue generation (Ochalibe, Okoye, & Enete, 2019). As a result of the increasing demand for food and other essential agricultural products, agriculture is regarded as the largest and most significant industry in the world. Agricultural productivity is important not only for a country's balance of trade but also for the security and health of its population. Growth in the agricultural sector has also played a crucial role in the reduction of poverty, and evidence of this can be seen in countries like China and India. However, the Nigerian economy has not yet been able to benefit from the potential of agriculture. Economists posit that some of the reasons for this include neglect of the sector by the Nigerian government, inadequate allocation of funds to the sector, and a lack of an enabling environment. However, recent arguments in the literature suggest that exchange rate movements may be a contributing factor (Adekunle Ndukwe, 2018; Emmanuel, 2019). Excessive volatility in the exchange rate creates uncertainty and risks for economic agents, with destabilising effects on the macroeconomy. Hence, failure to properly manage the exchange rate induces distortions in consumption and production patterns. Exchange rate movements have been empirically observed to cause

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instability in other core macroeconomic variables such as inflation, unemployment rate, consumer and producer prices, volume of goods and services produced, balance of payments, volume of trade, as well as a nation's growth rate. Thus, as stated by Mordi (2006), maintaining relative stability in exchange rate is imperative for both internal and external balance as well as growth in an economy.

Over the years, Nigeria has adopted considerable measures of trade liberalisation, including an effective rate of protection and a reduction in average tariff rates, as a way of achieving sustainable economic growth and development, of which agriculture is one of the key drivers (Okodua, Anyatowu, & Miapkwap, 2019). Trade liberalisation is the process of reducing or removing restrictions on international trade. This may include the reduction or removal of tariffs, the abolition or enlargement of import quotas, the abolition of multiple exchange rates, and the removal of requirements for administrative permits for imports or allocations of foreign exchange. Liberalisation of agriculture was more pronounced during the Uruguay Round 1986–1990 (Anowor, Ukwani, & Martins, 2013; Ifediba, 2019).

Economists generally see the concept of trade openness or trade liberalisation as the integration among the nations of the world; it is likened to the openness of the world economy, where nations link together to the extent of promoting financial activities (Igudia, 2014). Economic analysis informs us that openness to trade and the flow of factors, ideas, and information stimulate economic and political progress. Thus, openness to trade can be said to be the platform of globalisation, while trade, finance, investment, and entrepreneurs constitute the heart. In Nigeria, the term “trade liberalisation” became pronounced through the adoption of the IMF Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in 1986, which primary aim was to restructure and diversify the productive base of the economy. In addition, the SAP was also designed to establish a realistic and sustainable exchange rate for the Naira through trade and payment liberalisation, tariff reforms, commercialization, and privatisation (Anowor, 2013).

Trade liberalisation has been motivated by the urgent need to promote economic diversification, since relying on only crude oil portends great risk to the economy. Given the level of Nigeria's trade openness in 2016, which is over 20% compared to the 49% of the year 2000, the trade openness data has shown a fluctuating decline in the degree of openness for the Nigerian economy. Part of the reason for this could be a deliberate effort by the government to discourage foreign goods from flooding the Nigerian market and to encourage local production. However, this reality has a negative impact on the economy as competition in the market is reduced.

Ogundipe (2022) posits that one-way trade contributes to an increase in economic output is through comparative advantages, which create more value with the

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same resources. Competition typically stimulates real cost reduction, and the more competitive the situation that prevails after liberalisation, the more handwork is needed to reduce real costs than would be under the umbrella of protection. Politically, trade liberalisation brings about the interdependence of nations and encourages prospects for world peace. Akim (2014) puts it this way: "Trade liberalisation provides incentives for firms to compete, to innovate, and to search for new opportunities and markets, and firms in protected industries are less likely to innovate or seek new markets." Trade liberalisation is a key economic reform policy and institutional change adopted by Nigeria in 1986 to stimulate its exports (Afaha & Njogo, 2012). These authors are of the view that openness of trade is a policy measure that emphasises production and trade along the lines dictated by a country's comparative advantage, such as export promotion and export diversification, the reduction and elimination of import tariffs, and the adoption of market-determined exchange rates.

Olowe and Ibraheem (2015) stated that earlier thought on trade liberalisation policy was grounded by the works of Little, Scitovsky and Scott, Balassa, Bhagwati, and Kruenger. These studies provided the basis for trade liberalisation policies and the manner in which they are implemented. In recent years, trade in agriculture has not only attracted growing attention but is being viewed as the vehicle for global growth and equity. By expanding markets and removing distortions caused by high levels of protection in agriculture, global trade will not only facilitate competition but will also spur growth in an area that is linked directly to poverty and hunger. The main goal of agricultural trade has been said to be the provision of an enabling environment for a majority of the world's poorest to take advantage of the enormous opportunities to improve incomes and enjoy healthy lives. The World Bank estimated that more rapid growth associated with a global reduction in trade protection could reduce the number of people living in poverty by as much as 13 percent in 2015. In simple words, 300 million people could be pulled out of poverty.

It would appear that Nigeria's trade policy is driven more by events in the international oil market. A critical analysis shows that liberal trade policies prevail whenever there is an oil boom with attendant increases in oil prices and growth in government revenue. However, import restrictions, foreign exchange, and other physical controls assume dominance as soon as the oil boom ends. The government becomes sober (as it were), and inward-looking policies are once again put in place. For instance, benign government revenue occasioned by rising oil prices from 1973 to 1975 ensured a disproportionate increase in imports of relatively cheap foreign agricultural commodities like meat products, wheat flour, rice, and vegetable oils. The consequence of this policy was obvious: rising demand for these products due to the lack of competitiveness of local produce further constrained the capacity of domestic

producers. This is besides the attendant negative impact on Nigeria's balance of payments position. On the whole, the dominant feature of Nigeria's external trade policy during this period was “the protection of the domestic manufacturing sector at the expense of the agricultural sector” (Manyong et al., 2005; Effiom and Ebi, 2021).

Nigeria's trade policy under the SAP period was a general recognition of the obvious failures of state-led strategies to accelerate economic development. With a crippling debt burden, dilapidated and inadequate economic and social infrastructure to initiate any meaningful growth, an over-bloated public sector, a deflated private sector due to a hostile business environment, and dwindling government revenue occasioned by falling oil prices, it was apparent that some drastic measures needed to be taken to reverse the drift in the economy. Specifically, trade policy under this phase involved a radical overhaul of the existing tariff structure to protect local industries and domestic production of goods, domestic sourcing of raw materials, import substitution, and trade liberalisation. Indeed, Nigeria's trade liberalisation policy as it directly affected the agricultural sector involved the complete dismantling of commodity marketing boards, the abolition of most levies on imports, cuts in some export and excise duties, as well as a reduction by 75% in the mandatory advance payment of import duties when opening letters of credit (Manyong et al., 2005). There was also the promotion of exports of non-oil goods, especially agricultural commodities.

It has been theoretically argued that the difference in the rate of export rates could lead to differences in economic growth (Osabohien, Akinpelumi, Matthew, Okafor, Iku, Olawande, & Okorie, 2019). Export growth is recognised as a major contributor to productivity and the growth of employment in an economy, as evidenced in GDP growth rate. The favourable climatic conditions combined with good vegetation enable SSA countries to produce crops and livestock in particular (Osabuohie, Okorie, and Osabohien, 2018). The increase in agricultural exports has greatly benefited Nigeria; therefore, the relevance of exports to the financial development and progress of a country cannot be overemphasised as it helps to accelerate a country's overall progress. In addition, exports are a means of foreign exchange earnings due to the fact that trade activities between countries are settled in foreign exchange (Matthew et al., 2018). Job openings are created for their citizens, consequently reducing the social costs of unemployment (Osabohien and Bamigbola, 2017). The drive towards export promotion will boost an emerging nation's economic growth through the multiplier effects of exports on the income level of the country. This is because income earned through exports helps to enhance the aggregate demand in the country. Over the years, trade openness has attained a high degree in the Nigerian economy; thus, its efficiency should be promoted via the advancement of external trade. Primarily, agriculture has been the dominant sector of the Nigerian external sector (Osabohien and Osuagwu,

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2017). Agriculture has the distinguished features of low prices and unfavourable terms of trade earnings resulting from export instability. The low earnings from the export of agricultural commodities are due to the decrease in production of agricultural commodities, which made emerging economies rely on the importation of food. Among the very important objectives of emerging economies in general, and Nigeria in particular, is the achievement of accelerated overall wellbeing of the nation. In this regard, exports are seen as a promoting factor for economic growth (Adeleye, Osabuohien, Bowale, Matthew, & Oduntan, 2017).

It should be realised that the issue of trade policy and poverty is very contentious in the economic literature. As some scholars have acknowledged, poverty is not directly the result of international trade. Poverty is seen to reflect some conditions and situations, which include, but are not limited to, low earning power, few assets, poor access to communal resources, poor health and education, powerlessness, and vulnerability. Hence, Omoke (2006) argues that trade policy matters only to the extents (a) that it affects the direct determinants of poverty and (b) that, relative to the whole range of other possible policies, it offers an efficient policy lever for poverty alleviation. Thus, trade policy becomes relevant if it directly impacts employment, earnings, and resource allocation. Since these variables are influenced by relative prices in the system and since trade policy influences relative prices, then trade policy affects poverty and inequality. Much of the cost and benefits of trade policy reform have been related to the issue of the static and dynamic effects of trade. It is generally believed that if trade policy reform leads to higher growth, then, based on the trickle-down hypothesis, poverty and inequality will be reduced (Cornia, 2004; Omoke, 2006).

Theoretical framework

Two schools of thought (Adam Smith and David Ricardo) are of the opinion that foreign trade remains one of the major determinants of economic growth. The first school of thought focused on the elements, which are exogenously determined by the individual country. Such elements are the minimal growth rate resulting from low production of primary products in the market and the terms of trade, which are unfavourable. On the other hand, the second school of thought focused on the elements, which are endogenously determined by a country; those factors are the local institutions that have hampered agricultural exports (Osabohien, Afolabi, & Godwin, 2018). There is an obvious situation where no country is self-sufficient; nations inevitably trade with several others in order to enjoy goods and services for which they have a comparative weakness in their production while at the same time giving those goods a comparative advantage in their production. For example, in Nigeria, the masses are engaged in the agrarian section, while some are engaged in the manufacturing and tertiary sections.

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From the view of export-led growth theory, exports are the main determinants of the growth of the economy on the premise that higher exports generate higher earnings in the short term through the effect of foreign exchange multipliers. Second, higher exchange rises through higher exports, making purchases of machinery, electrical equipment, and transportation equipment easy. It is also used to buy fuel and food that can serve as catalysts for any country's economic growth. Third, the economic growth of a country is promoted indirectly via improvements in competition, economies of scale, and the development of technical know-how, among others. Fourth, externalities that are positive in nature, such as the effective control of inefficiencies in organisations, production management, and control, can be done by learning from foreign firms and experts who are knowledgeable about product design to enhance productivity (Adeleye, Osabuohien, Bowale, Matthew, & Oduntan, 2017).

The Arguments

Trade liberalisation, according to the protagonists, is economic integration for global output expansion, in that, with market liberalisation, investment funds can move unimpeded from industrialised countries to developing countries where they are most needed. Consumers can also benefit from cheaper products because reduced tariffs make goods produced from hi-tech industrialised countries cheaper to buy. In the same vein, producers of goods gain by selling to a wider market, while countries will benefit by gaining access to modern technology, negotiate for multilateral and/or bilateral trade. While antagonists argue that trade liberalisation is a conscious effort by the western world to deliberately force some of their economic policies that may not be favourable to the receiving economy with the aim of perpetually contributing to the underdevelopment of the less developed countries, it is seen as another form of post-colonialism strategy that does not promote self-reliance, self-determination, or indigenization (Ojoh, 2005). They also argued that the success of most developed nations is through protectionism and subsidies and not because of free trade (Ha-Joon, 2007). It is from this point of view that trade liberalisation is defined as integration towards a unified economic system dominated by supra-national countries and institutions that are not accountable to democratic processes or national governments (Richard, 2000). In addition, further reasons for the changing perception of liberalisation are, thus, the lack of tangible benefits to most developing countries from opening their economies, despite the well-publicised claims of export and income gains, which antagonists argue are even lesser than economic losses, and the social disorder rapid trade liberalisation has caused many developing countries; they also argue that trade liberalisation has led to growing inequalities of wealth and technology, decreasing

opportunities both at home and in the international community, and the perception that environmental, social, and cultural problems have been worsened by the workings of a free trade economy.

Empirical Review

Etuk, Igbodor, and Effiong (2017) analysed the effect of trade liberalisation policies on agricultural output growth in Nigeria using time series data from 1960–2014. The objectives were to estimate the differences in agricultural output before and after the trade liberalisation period and estimate the long and short run effects of agricultural trade policies on agricultural output in Nigeria. Data for the empirical study were sourced from various issues of the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) statistical bulletin and publications of the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the data. The estimation procedure was the co-integration and error correction model. The analysis revealed that the mean agricultural output after trade liberalisation (AGR GD2) was different from that of the pre-trade period (AGR GD1), and the t-test result confirms that there exists a significant difference between agricultural output during the pre-trade and post-trade liberalisation periods. The long-run and short-run regression results showed that trade openness and exchange rate had a negative effect on agricultural output in the three models, meaning that trade openness will lead to a reduction in agricultural output both in the long and short run. The study therefore recommended that monetary authorities should adopt policies that will reduce the volatility of the exchange rate. Also, the institution of import quota could curb the negative effect of trade openness on agricultural output growth in Nigeria.

Ojeyinka and Adegboye (2017) examined the impact of trade liberalisation on performance in the Nigerian economy, with special reference to the agricultural and manufacturing sectors. Simultaneous models were developed to capture the joint effects of trade liberalisation on the two sectors. The Generalised Method of Moment technique was used to estimate the role of trade liberalisation on the performance of the selected sectors. The study showed a significant positive impact of trade liberalisation on the output of the agricultural sector, while a negative but significant relationship exists between measures of trade liberalisation and manufacturing output in Nigeria. The study also revealed that the exchange rate exerts a positive but insignificant impact on agricultural output, while the effect of inflation on agricultural output is positive and significant within the study period. Unlike agricultural output, both the exchange rate and inflation have a negative impact on the manufacturing sector's output. Moreover, findings from the study also confirmed the possibility of substantial economic linkage between the two sectors, as their magnitudes were positive and significant, which

suggests some significant level of interdependence between them in the Nigerian economy. The study concluded that the government should embark on programmes that promote local production to fully harness the opportunity presented by trade liberalisation.

Sani and Yunusa (2019) assessed the impact of trade liberalisation in the agricultural sector on economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2016. The specific objectives of the paper were to assess the long run relationship between trade liberalisation and economic growth in Nigeria and to find out the short run dynamic between economic growth and trade liberalisation as well as the causal relationship between them. Data for the period 1981–2016 was elicited from the CBN statistical bulletin, the NBS Book of Abstracts, and WDI data. Findings showed that trade liberalisation and an appreciation in the level of the exchange rate exerted a positive impact on real economic growth in Nigeria. Thus, the study concluded that trade liberalisation is good for the Nigerian economy.

Okodua, Anyatonwu, and Miapkwap (2019) examined the impact of trade liberalisation on agricultural productivity in Nigeria using annual time series data from 1985 to 2017. Taking into account the causal relationship between trade liberalisation and agricultural productivity. The variables used in this study were foreign direct investment, degree of trade openness, tariffs as a proxy for trade liberalisation, fertiliser consumption, and capital expenditure as a proxy for agricultural productivity. The bounds test/ARDL approach to co-integration was used in the study to examine the long-run equilibrium relationship between trade liberalisation and agricultural productivity in Nigeria. The ARDL ECM was, however, used to determine the short run dynamics of the variables, while the pair-wise Granger causality test was used to determine the dimension of causality between the relationship of trade liberalisation and agricultural productivity. Results from the study, however, showed a positive and significant relationship between trade liberalisation and agricultural productivity in Nigeria. The study revealed that foreign direct investment, tariffs, fertiliser consumption, and capital expenditures conformed to a priori expectations and were significant, apart from foreign direct investment and tariffs, which were found to be insignificant. The degree of trade openness did not conform to the a priori expectation but was found to be significant. The study suggested that more foreign investment should be encouraged and directed towards the agricultural sector to improve agricultural sector productivity.

Orji et al. (2019) examined the impact of exchange rate movements on the agricultural sector in Nigeria. Time series data and the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation technique were employed in the study to address the specified objectives.

The variables employed in the study were exchange rate, agricultural GDP, government capital expenditure, foreign direct investment, credit to the private sector, and lending interest rate. The result showed that exchange rate movements play a significant role in the agricultural sector's performance in Nigeria. Specifically, the findings showed that exchange rate, government capital expenditure, foreign direct investment, and lending interest rate were positively related to agricultural GDP, while credit to the private sector was negatively related. The co-integration approach was also applied to determine the long-run relationship between the variables. The results revealed that the variables have a statistically significant impact on the agricultural sector in the long run. The study recommended that the apex bank should keep a close watch on exchange rate developments in order to enhance exchange rate stability, which will contribute to the development of the agricultural sector.

Obiageli (2020) examined the effects of the exchange rate on agricultural sector output in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to: determine the effect of the nominal exchange rate on agricultural sector output in Nigeria; examine the effect of money supply on agricultural sector output in Nigeria; analyse the effect of the interest rate on agricultural sector output in Nigeria; and determine the effect of the inflation rate on agricultural sector output in Nigeria. To analyse the data, econometric techniques involving Augmented Dickey Fuller tests for unit roots and the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) were used. The result of the regression indicated that the nominal exchange rate and money supply have a positive and significant effect on agricultural sector output, while the interest rate and inflation rate have a negative and insignificant effect on agricultural sector output. The study therefore concluded that exchange rates have an adverse effect on the performance of agricultural sector output and have not helped to improve the rate of investment in agriculture in Nigeria. The study recommended that there is a need for the government to ensure the implementation of policies that will encourage local agricultural growth in order to reduce imports by providing price policies, perfect markets, and credit facilities to work side by side with crude oil production.

Effiom and Ebi (2021) investigated, using the autoregressive distributed lag methodology, the impact of Nigeria's trade policy and infrastructural development on agricultural value added. Findings showed that in the long run, Nigeria's trade liberalisation policy is disincentive to the growth of the agricultural sector's value added, while key components of infrastructure (roads, telecommunications, and electricity consumption) had a significant relationship and positive impact on the agricultural sector. Inter alia, the paper recommended that the government strengthen the current selective ban on some agricultural products while implementing the recommendations of the African Development Bank Infrastructure Plan for Nigeria.

Udoh and Adelaja (2021) focused on the impact of trade policies on the exportation of agricultural commodities in Nigeria. A total of three hundred and seventy (370) certified exporters of agricultural commodities were randomly selected for the study. The data was analysed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis. Results showed that the major agricultural trade policy actions that positively impacted export commodity productivity and supply volume were the Anchor Borrowers Programme, duty-free imports of agricultural equipment, and the Nigerian Incentive-Based Risk Sharing System for Agricultural Lending. Constraints faced by the exporters include high transportation costs, unfavourable weather conditions, unfavourable government policy, and so on. Moreover, educational level, experience, source of farmland used for cultivation, and source of seedlings were significantly related to the period when exporters supplied the highest volume of agricultural commodities. The study recommended that favourable policies for exporters of agricultural commodities should be enacted.

Ogunjinmi and Oduyoye-Ejumedia (2021) investigated the impact of trade openness and the domestic currency rate on agricultural performance in Nigeria within the period 1981–2019. Using the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) approach, the study confirmed that there exists a long-run relationship between trade policy and agricultural performance in Nigeria. The result showed that trade openness has a significant and positive effect on agricultural performance in Nigeria. Further, the study confirmed that trade openness contributes more to agricultural performance in the long run than in the short run. However, the exchange rate had a negative and significant impact on agricultural performance in the long run. Meanwhile, the short-run estimates showed that the exchange rate has a significant and positive effect on agricultural performance. More so, it was gathered that the interest rate affects agricultural performance negatively in Nigeria. There is a need for the government to embark on an outward-looking trade policy that supports the agricultural industry in terms of its exportation of indigenous commodities and stimulation of output growth.

Udoh and Adelaja (2021) assess the impact of agricultural trade policies and export values of agricultural commodities on GDP in Nigeria. The study made use of time series data. The Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test (unit root test) and regression analysis were used to assess the data. According to the data, cocoa and cashew had the highest export value in 2012, while ginger had the highest export value in 2013. Between 2010 and 2018, fourteen (14) agricultural policies were enacted, which included the Bank of Agriculture, the Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme (CACS), duty-free imports of agricultural equipment, the Growth Enhancement Support Scheme, the Nigeria Incentive-Based Risk Sharing System for Agricultural Lending

(NIRSAL), and others. Findings revealed that a significant relationship existed between trade policy and agriculture's contribution to GDP. It is advised that favourable policies such as reduced import duties and friendly import tariffs should be implemented.

John (2021) examined the relationship between financial sector liberalisation and agricultural sector output in Nigeria using annual data spanning the period 1986–2020. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to examine the relationship between lending rate, exchange rate, commercial bank credit to agriculture, inflation rate, and agricultural sector output in Nigeria. Ex-post facto research design was employed, and the annual time series data were collated from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin. The econometric methods of unit root, co-integration, and error correction mechanisms were used for the analyses. The outcome of the ADF unit root test showed that the variables were stationary. Also, the co-integration result showed that there is co-integration amongst the variables in the model. The results from the Error Correction Model indicated that lending rates and inflation rates have a negative relationship with agricultural sector output, while exchange rates and commercial bank credit to agriculture have a positive relationship with agricultural sector output. Based on these results, the study recommended that the government and policymakers in Nigeria should undertake policies that will boost investments in the agricultural sector through the direct provision of credits to agriculturists, and banks should also lend at a very low and subsidised interest rate to enable farmers' access to agricultural loans that will boost agricultural productivity in the economy.

Trade policies, especially as they concern the agricultural sector, have been formulated to ensure increased productivity in the sector. Various pieces of literature reviewed above present mixed results as to the impact of trade policies on the performance of the agriculture sector in Nigeria. While exchange rate regimes and trade openness had been used in most of the studies to determine the degree of performance of the sector, much attention had not been given to the extent to which agriculture sector performance could be influenced by tariff regime change. The present study incorporates this variable in addition to exchange rate and trade openness.

Research Methodology

Research Design

The research design adopted for this study is a time-series *ex-post facto* design. The adoption of this technique is predicated on the fact that the data are taken as given and the researchers' ability to manipulate the data is restricted.

Variables of Study

The study is particularly about trade policies and agricultural sector performance in Nigeria. Given the various trade policies, this study adopted exchange rate policies, trade liberalisation policies, and tariff regime policies. On the other hand, agriculture sector performance is measured by the contribution of agriculture sector GDP to the total GDP. Thus, variables of the study are: agriculture sector performance, denoted by contribution of each sub-sector of the agriculture sector to total GDP; exchange rate; trade openness; and tariffs on agriculture exports and imports.

Data measurement and source

The variables of the study, as specified above, are agriculture sector performance and trade policy. Agriculture sector performance is measured as the ratio of agriculture sector GDP to total real GDP. Trade policy is measured by several trade policy regimes, like the exchange rate regime, trade liberalisation, and tariff regime. Foreign exchange regime is measured by exchange rate, trade liberalisation by trade openness is calculated as the ratio of the sum of imports and exports to GDP, and tariffs are measured as the share of tariff lines with international peak as a percentage of primary products. Exchange rate data was obtained from the 2021 Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin. Data for trade openness was computed by the author with data from the CBN statistical bulletin, 2021, while tariff data was obtained from the World Development Indicators (WDI) bulletin.

Model Specification

The study sought to examine the effect of trade policy on agriculture sector performance. Having identified the variables of study above, the model is specified as;

$$ASP = f(excr, topn, tarf) \quad (1)$$

Where ASP = Agriculture Sector Performance

EXCR = exchange rate

TOPN = trade openness

TARF = tariff

Econometrically, (1) can be written as;

$$ASP = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 Exch + \beta_2 Topn + \beta_3 Tarf + \mu_i \quad (2)$$

α_0 = intercept; β_1, β_3 = parameters; μ_i = error term

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Estimation Technique

The model (2) specified above was estimated econometrically using Ordinary Least Square (OLS) estimation technique. Prior to estimation, the variables were subjected to unit root test for stationarity to ascertain the level of integration of each variable.

IV. Data Analysis and Interpretation of Results

Table 4.1: Unit Root Test of Stationarity

Variables	ADF statistics	1%	5%	10%	Remark	I(d)
AGDP	4.8537	4.2927	3.5683	3.2183	Constant, linear trend	1(1)***
Exch	3.7656	3.6701	2.9639	2.6210	constant	1(1)***
Tarf	6.5011	3.6701	2.9639	2.6210	constant	1(1)***
Topn	5.2689	3.6701	2.9639	2.6210	constant	1(1)***

*** significant at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively

The table above shows that all the variables were integrated of order 1 i.e., 1(1). The implication is that there is a long-term relationship among the variables. In addition, the variables can be regressed at their level of integration without the possibility of spurious regression.

Table 4.2: The Effect of Trade Policy on Agriculture Sector Performance

Dependent variable: Agriculture Sector Performance (AGDP)

Method: Least squares

Variables	Coeff.	Std.error	t-stat.	Prob.
C	20832.98	1399.684	14.8841	0.0000
Exch	13.5307	3.1509	4.2941	0.0002
Tarf	-1.56E+09	1.40E+08	-11.1852	0.0000
Topn	-72.8922	20.3405	-3.5835	0.0013
R² = 0.98	Adj.R² = 0.97	DW = 1.47		

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The table above attempts to show the relationship between agriculture sector performance and components of trade policy in addition to answering the research questions. From the table above, it can be noticed that a positive and significant relationship exist between exchange rate and agriculture sector performance. The relationship between tariff and agriculture sector performance is negative and significant. Furthermore, there is a negative and significant relationship between trade openness and agriculture sector performance.

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

Exchange rate liberalisation has no significant relationship with agriculture sector performance in Nigeria. From the table 4.2 above, the outcome shows that there is a positive and significant relationship between exchange rate as a component of trade policy and agriculture sector performance. On the strength of this, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Trade openness has no significant relationship with agriculture sector performance in Nigeria. There is a negative and significant relationship between trade openness and agriculture sector performance. The null hypothesis of non-significant relations is thereby rejected.

Test of Hypothesis Three

Tariff liberalisation has no significant relationship with agriculture sector performance in Nigeria. There is a negative and significant relationship between tariff regime and agriculture sector performance. The null hypothesis of non-significant relationship is again rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The study was concerned with examining the relationship between trade policy and agriculture sector performance in Nigeria between 1990 and 2021. From the empirical results presented, it has been found that trade policy has a significant relationship with agriculture sector performance. The agriculture sector comprises four subsectors, namely: crop production, livestock, fishery, and forestry. The extent to which each of these sub-sectors had been affected by trade policy shows that an appreciation in the exchange rate will result in increased performance in each agriculture sub-sector. Exchange rate is the price at which a country's domestic currency exchanges with the

currency of trade on the international market. In this case, the currency of exchange was the US dollar. The implication is that if the price at which Nigerian agriculture sector products are sold on the international market is high, this will invariably boost agriculture sector production with a view to reaping high foreign exchange earnings from international trade.

Tariffs are seen to indicate a significant negative relationship with agriculture sector performance. This relationship is appropriate in view of the fact that if tariffs on imported agriculture sector intermediate goods such as machines and fertiliser are reduced, increased production will be enhanced, ensuring a higher performance of the sector. Conversely, if the tariff on the export of agricultural products is reduced, this will no doubt increase exports and invariably increase production capacity in the sector.

Trade openness has both a negative and positive impact on the performance of the agriculture sector in Nigeria. Trade openness encourages competitiveness. If trade openness results in importing more food into the country than exporting it, it will reduce the performance of the sector, especially in the areas of livestock, fishing, and crop production. Thus, the negative sign of trade openness indicates that trade openness in favour of imports will result in poor performance in the sector, especially in the area of food production. Conversely, trade openness in favour of exports will enhance greater productivity in the sector, as this will also tend to increase competitiveness.

From the presented results, it can be further said that the model is a proper fit, as the R^2 and adjusted R^2 indicate. What this implies is that 98% of the variation in the agriculture sector could be explained by the appropriate trade policy, which consists of proper exchange rate management, proper tariff regime management, and effective trade openness.

Summary, Conclusion, and Recommendations

The study sought to examine the relationship between trade policy and agriculture sector performance in Nigeria between 1990 and 2021. Specifically, the study examined the relationship between exchange rate and agriculture sector performance, the relationship between tariffs and agriculture sector performance, and the relationship between trade openness and agriculture sector performance. Three research questions and three research hypotheses were formulated and tested in the study. Data for the study was obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin and World Development Indicators. Ordinary least squares (OLS) in a single equation technique was used in estimating the study model. From the results, it was found that a positive and significant relationship exists between exchange rate and agriculture sector performance, a negative and significant relationship between tariff and agriculture

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sector performance, and a negative and significant relationship exists between tariff and agriculture sector performance. The R^2 of 0.98 indicates that 98% of the variation in the dependent variable was explained by the independent variables.

The essence of various trade policies has been to improve the performance of the sector to which they are directed. Trade policies directed at agriculture sector performance had not been found to significantly impact the performance of the sector. The present study has shown that trade policy directed towards improvement in the performance of the agriculture sector should look at the exchange rate regime, ensure trade openness does not impact negatively on the performance of the sector, and tariff should not be discriminating.

From the findings of the study, the following suggestions are worth considering:

1. Since the foreign exchange market is volatile, the government should ensure that there is a workable exchange rate regime, especially for the real sector of the economy, using the proper channel for demand and supply of foreign exchange in the agriculture sector. A favourable exchange regime is believed to increase agriculture sector production and earn foreign exchange for the economy through exports.
2. The policy of trade openness should be directed at promoting more exports than imports. This could be achieved by ensuring the competitiveness of the sector. Proper implementation of trade policy regarding the agriculture sector should not be handled with kid gloves.
3. A favourable tariff regime that encourages exports would promote domestic production and reduce agriculture imports except for essential agriculture inputs.

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